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CULTURAL IDEA OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN RUSSIA AND ITS DEVELOPMENT AT THE END OF THE 20TH AND BEGINNING OF THE 21ST CENTURIES

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Abstract. In pedagogy, culture contributes to the formation of personality and has significant pedagogical and educational potential. In the late 20th and early 21st centuries, educational scientists increasingly note the relationship between culture and the discipline "Foreign language" as a fact of the formation moral and aesthetic consciousness of the individual. The development of the cultural idea in teaching foreign languages in Russia during the specified period of time is studied. The main goal is to study the development of factors promoting the learning of foreign languages in the context of cultural dialogue. The research task is to analyze the influence of the culturological idea on the methodology of teaching foreign languages in Russia at the end of the 20th - beginning of the 21st century. Attention is drawn to the importance of familiarizing students with cultural studies material for understanding a different culture, developing readiness to communicate in a foreign language environment, tolerance and respect. The culturological approach is considered as one of the strategically important approaches of that time, in which culture acts as the core in the process of teaching foreign languages. Examples of differences in the communicative behavior of different peoples are given; the main sources of cultural knowledge (text-books) are demonstrated. It is concluded that becoming a participant in intercultural communication, the student must learn to accept a different culture, its values and advantages. The cultural potential is the strategic objective of the subject "Foreign language", which means that the study of foreign languages must necessarily take place in the context of culture.

Keywords: culture, culturological approach, cultural dialogue, foreign languages, intercultural communication, mutual understanding

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КУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ИДЕЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ В РОССИИ В КОНЦЕ XX НАЧАЛЕ XXI ВВ.

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Аннотация. В педагогике культура способствует становлению личности и обладает значительным образовательным и воспитательным потенциалом. В конце XX начале XXI вв. ученые-педагоги все больше отмечают взаимосвязь культуры и дисциплины «Иностранный язык», как факт формирования нравственного и эстетического сознания личности. Изучено развитие культурологической идеи в обучении иностранным языкам в России в указанный период времени. Основной целью является изучение развития факторов, содействующих обучению иностранных языков в контексте диалога культур. Задачей исследования является анализ влияния культурологической идеи на методику обучения иностранным языкам в России в конце XX - начале XXI века. Обращено внимание на важность знакомства обучающихся с культуроведческим материалом для понимания иной культуры, развития готовности к общению в иноязычной среде, толерантности и уважения. Рассмотрен культурологический подход как один из стратегически важных подходов того времени, в котором культура выступает ядром в процессе преподавания иностранных языков. Приведены примеры различий в коммуникативном поведении разных народов; продемонстрированы основные источники культурологических знаний (учебники). Сделан вывод, что становясь участником межкультурной коммуникации, обучающийся должен научиться принимать иную культуру, ее ценности, достоинства и преимущества. Культурологический потенциал составляет стратегическую задачу предмета «Иностранный язык», а это значит, изучение иностранных языков должно обязательно происходить в контексте культуры.

Ключевые слова: культура, культуроведческий подход, диалог культур, иностранные языки, межкультурная коммуникация, взаимопонимание

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Introduction

The economic, socio-political, and spiritual transformation of Russian society in the late 1980s brought about significant alterations in the perception of culture, redefining its core essence. Much attention is beginning to be paid to the importance of culture in everyday life and in society, which eventually brought the methodology to professional cultural education. There is also a new ideal of the future specialist, namely: a man of culture. Ideological pluralism, in which the formation of this ideal takes place, presupposes a variety of means for the creative realization of personality in cultural education.

Actively developing international contacts, relations in politics, economics and culture have gradually reoriented the methodology of teaching foreign languages to real communication conditions. The attainment of communicative competence is the ultimate outcome of the educational process, encompassing the following elements:

- 1) proficiency in foreign language technology, i.e. language competence;
- 2) assimilation of a sufficiently large amount of non-linguistic information that is necessary for successful communication.

Language users originating from different linguistic backgrounds demonstrate distinguishable attributes stemming from their unique historical, cultural, socioeconomic, political, and environmental circumstances within their respective communities. Hence, it becomes imperative to cultivate a deep understanding of the intricate nuances related to the specific country associated with the target language. As a result, the inclusion of cultural ideologies becomes indispensable in the domain of Russian foreign language education.

Within the purview of this paper, a thorough examination is conducted to explore the transformative journey of foreign language education in Russia, specifically focusing on the period encompassing the late 20th and early 21st centuries. The principal aim of this endeavor is to critically assess the various influential elements that have played a pivotal role in shaping the pedagogy of foreign languages, particularly within the framework of intercultural communication and interaction.

Methodology

The materials for the article were scientific works by Russian scholars on the value potential of

the cultural idea in teaching foreign languages. The emphasis on culture in Russian education is its fundamental component. An important contribution to the development of the cultural idea in Russia at the end of the twentieth century was made by V. S. Bibler. His reflections and research on the role of culture in education are reflected in the works of modern teachers and methodologists. I. L. Bim, E. I. Passov, A. D. Reichstein, V. V. Safonova, E. N. Solovova, V. P. Sysoev, S. G. Ter-Minasova, G. D. Tomakhin wrote about the key role of culture as a dialogue. Teachers addressed the issues of co-learning language and culture, as well as developed the theoretical foundations of learning foreign languages from a cultural perspective.

When learning a new language, we first need to learn the culture of a foreign country, i.e. learning should be comparative. It is possible to understand the culture of the country of the studied language only when recognizing something new in one's own. There are many opinions on this subject, for example, P. V. Sysoev wrote that a deep and complete understanding of native culture will provide good results in the study of foreign culture [7].

The familiarization of students with cultural studies material, which provides an understanding of another culture, develops their abilities such as willingness to communicate in a foreign environment, tolerance and respect. As practice shows, the successful assimilation of knowledge about the culture of the country of the studied language is influenced by comparison and comparison with knowledge about the native culture. "Cultural symbols played a fundamental role in socialization, one of their key societal functions" [12].

Results

In the 80-90 years of the 20th century, a culturalological approach in order to comprehend and understand another culture for successful communication has become a strategically important approach in teaching a foreign language. In 1985, "The Final Act of the Conference on Security and Cooperation" in Europe was held in Helsinki, where a special section "Foreign languages and civilizations" was allocated. The European States expressed their determination to encourage the study of foreign languages and civilizations in order to expand communication between peoples, familiarize them with culture and strengthen international cooperation [10].

One of the variants of the cultural approach in teaching foreign languages in Russia has become the linguistic and regional approach (or cognitive and regional), which was developed by G.D. Tomakhin in 1980 and those approaches were focused on the co-study of language and culture. The essence of this approach, according to the scientist, is that the assimilation of the material occurs together with the study of the history and culture of the country [10].

A. D. Reichstein describes two ways of gradual development of cultural ideas and presentation of regional information in the classroom. The first is a thematic method that presents important data about history, geography, the state system and culture. This systematization of country-specific information goes well with basic language training. The second, philological method, which extracts regional information from foreign language structures (words, phrases, sentences, texts) and is implemented exclusively in the process of learning speech [4]. The training curriculum incorporates both regional-specific information and appropriate linguistic expression in the target language.

Methodologists M. I. Burdina and L. A. Shemarulina, of the RSFSR, publish a study on the topic "Teaching a foreign language in schools of the RSFSR and ways to improve it" (1984). In this paper, they refer to the draft of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union "Main directions of reforming general education and vocational schools", which defines ways to further development of education and improve the quality of the educational process.

One of the points of this project was: 1) expanding the horizons of students; 2) enriching them with information about geography, history, literature, art, and everyday life of the country of the studied language [1]. The authors describe in detail a new series of educational and methodical complexes of 1980-1981, which firmly took its place in the educational process in foreign languages.

As an academic discipline, "Foreign language" begins to occupy an important place among the means of educational influence on students. Extracurricular work on the subject helps to increase the level of proficiency in oral speech and reading, develops general

motivation to study language and culture. M. I. Burdina and L. A. Shemarulina write that in schools of that time there was a concept of holding circles and evenings in a foreign language, as well as a week of a foreign language. International friendship clubs were particularly popular, where teachers and students had the opportunity to share their experiences [1].

In subsequent times, there was a further amplification in the range of cultural methodologies, such as linguocultural, ethnocultural, multicultural, and other similar approaches. In these methodologies, culture serves as the fundamental foundation upon which the entirety of language teaching is predicated. The advent and evolution of multiple alternatives of the cultural approach corresponded to the urgent needs of our country's expanding international relations with other states in order to better understand representatives of other countries and cultures.

Foreign languages are a means of international communication, and mastering them without studying and understanding culture is almost impossible. Students must not only excelling in the studied language but also maintaining a strong connection with one's own native culture. In studying and comparing cultures mentalities, lifestyles, worldviews, customs, traditions, and behaviors in society need to be taken into account. First of all, learning foreign languages is an acquaintance with culture, which directly affects the multicultural development of a person.

Learning foreign languages is increasingly being seen as a valuable skill that could facilitate international communication and cultural exchange. This period can be described as establishing international contacts and a chance to expand professional opportunities. The collapse of the Soviet Union and the fall of the Iron Curtain are beginning to change the country's geopolitical landscape. The need to speak foreign languages in order to communicate with the now open world for successful interaction with foreign partners is beginning to grow.

The late 80s – early 90s were the beginning of the reform of higher education. It was derived from:

- The democratization and autonomization of universities have made a huge progress,
- The grounding of education programs has taken place,

- Decentralization of university administration,
- The philosophy of humanization,
- Education began to be diversified and multi-level structures were introduced.

Developmental learning and active learning theories are actively developing and interest in innovative ideas and the pedagogy of cooperation is increasing.

The cultural landscape of foreign language learning underwent profound transformations in the 1990s, marked by a fundamental shift towards international communication as a medium of exchange between individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. Consequently, the co-study of language and culture forms the basis for an effective and fruitful intercultural dialogue. The discipline "Foreign language" is no longer a process of learning vocabulary, phonetics and grammar, but is an intercultural education and comprehension of the culture of the studied language.

The year 1990 is marked as a new stage in the development of school education. Economic, political and social changes have led to a rethinking of methodological theory, which is now based on: a humanistic manifestation of cooperation, respect and tolerance for bearers of other views. Consequently, there is an increasing need to create new methodological ideas, approaches, manuals and programs.

In 1992, the Law of the Russian Federation "On Education" was issued, which, however, did not solve the hopes placed on it in the field of reforming the entire educational system. The legislation set forth the objective of education – to guarantee the attainment of a comprehensive and proficient cultural standard for society, the development of a student's perception of the world that aligns with contemporary knowledge and the educational curriculum (stage of study). The document also spoke about the need to integrate the individual into modern society, aimed at its improvement, as well as into national and world culture.

The field of sociolinguistics provides various methodological approaches for analyzing how culture and society intersect with language. It encompasses a socio-cultural examination of linguistic situations to uncover the underlying socio-cultural context.

In 1992, V.V. Safonova developed the socio-cultural approach to foreign language teaching as a special-

ized field. According to the socio-cultural approach, foreign language teaching is inextricably linked to the ethnic, religious, and social aspects of the culture of the studied language. A foreign language is becoming a "powerful tool for students' socio-cultural education" [5].

The 1990s witnessed a substantial broadening of the role of foreign language as a subject in Russia, owing to profound political, socio-economic, and cultural transformations. Consequently, these changes have led to a rethinking of the goals, objectives and content of teaching the subject in new curricula and teaching materials. Linguodidacts develop new and improve existing approaches to teaching foreign languages. Such cultural approaches as: linguistic, regional, literary, cross-cultural, sociocultural significantly facilitate the co-study of language and culture. In general, this period of time was aimed at integrating various aspects of culture into the learning system.

Due to social changes, the formation of social and state orders, by the end of the twentieth century, domestic scientific research in the field of intercultural communication theory began to be actively carried out. The initiators of the development of the problem of mutual understanding of cultures and their representatives were teachers of foreign languages of domestic universities, psychologists, sociologists and linguists. They developed a theoretical basis for developing the problem of the relationship between different cultures, formed ideas about the communication process, about cross-cultural communication, about interethnic communication and intercultural communication.

During this period, interest in the concept of "cultural person" is reviving in the public consciousness. Pedagogical science conceptually turns to the ideas of cultural pedagogy. From the point of view of culture, a new paradigm of education is emerging, in which the main goal is the formation of a highly developed personality.

In the late 90s and early 2000s, the era of accelerating globalization. The inception of a unified economic market and the blending of diverse cultures commenced. In June 1999, the Bologna Declaration was endorsed by 29 nations in their endeavor to align higher education with Western European counterparts and create a single European higher education area. Today, the Bologna Process covers 48 countries.

As the new millennium commenced of XXI century, crucial documents were formulated, elucidating the strategic aims and objectives of the national education system, along with the primary avenues for progress across all its tiers. "National Doctrine of Education in the Russian Federation" (2000), "The Concept of modernization of Russian education for the period up to 2010" (2002), the Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" (2012).

The important task of forming a respectful attitude to a foreign culture actualizes the purpose of learning a foreign language – to give students an idea of the universality of any language in order to form a person's communicative needs and respect for the languages and cultures of the peoples of the country of the studied language, which affects the formation of personality.

At the beginning of the XXI century, S. G. Ter-Minasova's great work "Language and Intercultural Communication" (2000) was published, which explores the close relationship between language and culture, where language is a reflection of culture (morality, values, mentality, worldview, etc.). She writes that "Language is a tool, an instrument of culture. It forms the personality of a person, a native speaker, through the vision of the world imposed on him by language and embedded in language, mentality, attitude towards people, etc., that is, through the culture of the people using this language as a means of communication" [9].

So, we understand that the relationship between language and culture is a rather complicated issue.

The author sees that studying foreign language is a cultural crossroad, which offer us a practice of intercultural communication. Every foreign language word learned in the classroom is a reflection of the foreign 'other' world and culture, and every word is an expression of a national consciousness and world. Russian foreign language education is beginning to experience a difficult period of restructuring and reevaluation of values. Modern times require new specific methods and techniques for teaching foreign languages.

E. I. Passov is developing a program-concept of communicative foreign language education "The development of individuality in the dialogue of cultures" (2000). A foreign language cannot simply exist in society and live its own life, it is directly related to such

spheres of social activity as economics, politics, art, etc. The author calls a foreign language the guardian of another culture, which reveals another world and fosters respect for another people [3].

In this work, E. I. Passov touches on such an important aspect as mutual understanding in intercultural dialogue. Inter-European and intercontinental relations are based on mutual understanding, which in turn is facilitated by the result of learning foreign languages. According to the author, mutual understanding consists of three aspects: 1) sociological (understanding the community and dependence of one culture on another); 2) socio-cultural (acquiring the socio-cultural status of speech and non-speech behavior); 3) axiological value (awareness and understanding of the values of another culture); 4) psychological (cooperation in co-experience and empathy, removal of semantic barriers)

Thus, we understand that mutual understanding is "understanding the language of the people plus respect for their culture" [3]. Recognition of other people's values, rights and respect is an example of successful mutual understanding between peoples.

So, the language policy of the state begins to correspond to new political, economic and social realities. A foreign language is a productive force, and foreign language literacy becomes an "economic category". There are changes in attitudes towards the subject, which is a condition for the progress of society. Language and culture become one and language is not considered separately, but only as an integral part of culture. Knowledge-centered education is shifting to a culturally-based one and makes the student not only educated, but also cultured. Culturally oriented education aims to teach thinking, to educate a morally responsible and socially adapted person [3].

P. V. Sysoev wrote about the 90s as the beginning of integration into the world community in his study "The Concept of linguistic multicultural education" (2004). Building an open democratic society has set the following goal for Russian education, namely, "educating students with a planetary mindset, i.e. capable of considering themselves not only as representatives of national culture living in a particular country, but also as citizens of the world, perceiving themselves as subjects of a dialogue of cultures and realizing their role, significance, responsibility in global universal processes" [8].

Thus, the matter of individual self-determination is introduced in view of acknowledging one's position within the cultural realm. Psychologically speaking, self-determination involves engaging in a process of self-realization within the framework of the sociocultural context that surrounds an individual.

The author believed that in order to optimize the process of cultural self-determination through foreign languages. The introduction of multiculturalism and the multicultural approach in foreign language teaching, as proposed by P. V. Sysoev, suggests that language instruction should be guided by a consideration of cultural diversity. Multiculturalism in language teaching entails incorporating the diverse cultural aspects into the pedagogical and methodological framework of foreign language education. It encompasses social, religious, ethnic, regional, professional, and other relevant cultural facets. This approach promotes a more favorable setting for the multicultural development of students, enabling them to explore languages and cultures simultaneously. It can also encourage them to study the comparison between one's own culture and others. Through this process, students acquire a deeper understanding of the socio-cultural landscape and their own position within it. [8].

The introduction of students to a foreign culture through a foreign language and the co-study of language and culture is becoming an urgent topic in Russian pedagogy. Over the past decade, scientists and methodologists have focused on such issues as the development of a socio-cultural approach to learning, which was carried out by V. V. Safonova (1991-2000), E. N. Solovova (1997), P. V. Sysoev (1999), V. P. Furmanova (1994).

In addition to examining the formation of sociocultural competence through foreign languages, scholars also focused on the definition of the multicultural component of educational content and the creation of additional courses in cultural studies. This topic was explored by V. V. Safonova in 1995 and 2001, as well as P. V. Sysoev in 1998-1999. Furthermore, researchers like V. V. Safonov in 1996 and 1999, and E. N. Grom in 1999, conducted studies on the formation of sociocultural competence through foreign languages. During this period, there was also an analysis of the joint study of language and culture, as well as the parallel study of native and foreign culture in foreign language classes.

In early 2005, V. V. Safonova and P. V. Sysoev, referring to the "Concept of modernization of Russian education for the period up to 2010" [6]. At that time, a system of vocational training was established. This system included elective courses in American cultural studies. This course is part of the humanitarian and philological profile of education and serves as an in-house specialization of students in learning foreign languages (English) [6].

The presented course aims at several objectives according to the authors' perspective. First, it aims to develop students' ability to use English as an educational and self-educational tool in the field of cultural and linguistic studies. Second, the combined study of the language and culture of the country impacts artistic and aesthetic development. Lastly, the course aims to build communicative competence in exploring world culture and facilitating intercultural communication.

The Cultural Studies course is designed to provide an interdisciplinary link between the discipline of foreign languages and other topics in the human cycle and includes 17 cultural topics, such as: introduction to cultural studies, history and cultural roots of English, international functions of English, American symbols and national memory, religious and cultural portrait of the USA, socio-cultural characteristics the social strata of American society, the socio-cultural portrait of the American family and others. These topics will close gaps in the humanitarian training of students, as well as increase the level of general cultural skills.

Therefore, V. V. Safonova and P. V. Sysoev have taken a remarkable initiative by designing a humanities course that focuses on cultural studies in the United States. This course is built upon fundamental principles of cultural studies education, with a key emphasis on using a foreign language as a medium. These principles encompass various aspects such as cultural reflection, co-learning the language within the context of cultural discourse, promoting cultural diversity and ensuring educational compatibility, and fostering the development of a multicultural and bilingual persona [6]. Through the creation of this course, a significant stride has been made in enriching students' socio-cultural education through the utilization of a foreign language.

Studying the varied cultures and linguistic backgrounds fosters an understanding of cultural diversity as a natural aspect of coexistence in today's globalized world. Exploring the breadth of cultures and languages nurtures an appreciation for the rich tapestry of diversity that characterizes our interconnected world. By immersing themselves in the study of different societies and their unique practices, students gain a deep understanding of how cultural pluralism is an intrinsic part of modern coexistence. This knowledge broadens our perspectives, fuels curiosity, and encourages a genuine celebration of the myriad ways in which human beings experience and express their identities. In embracing cultural diversity as a fundamental pillar of our globalized society, we foster an environment that encourages mutual respect, curiosity, and collaboration.

Thus, at the end of the twentieth century, a fairly serious scientific basis for considering the cultural idea in teaching foreign languages was being formed.

Discussion

The students' capacity to uncover cultural phenomena plays a crucial role in comprehending the culture of the country associated with the studied language. Take, for example, the "smile" in the communicative behavior of a Russian and an American. In the context of Russian communication, distinct national characteristics are associated with the act of smiling. Unlike the American communication style, where smiling is commonly perceived as a gesture of politeness, the case is found to be quite the contrary within Russian culture. In Russia, a person who consistently exhibits a smiling demeanor is often referred to as a "giving a galvanic smile," a portrayal indicative of a lack of sincerity and an inclination towards secrecy. A common expression "broken smile" is also used to describe someone who smiles solely out of politeness, thereby highlighting the unfavorable perception towards such individuals. Moreover, the act of smiling in Russia is predominantly directed towards familiar acquaintances, as exemplified by the scarcity of smiling salespeople within stores. Reciprocal smiling in response to a smile is not customary, as this prompts Russian individuals to contemplate the underlying motives behind the display of affability. If a Russian person unintentionally makes eye contact with

someone, they are more likely to avoid maintaining their gaze, whereas an American would typically respond with a smile. In the realm of Russian communicative culture, the hallmarks of sincerity and openness are prominent, underscoring the significance attributed to a smile as a genuine reflection of one's personal disposition towards the interlocutor.

The manner in which greetings are carried out reveals contrasting patterns of communicative behavior between individuals hailing from Russia and France, exemplifying their distinct cultural inclinations. This distinction particularly manifests in the democratic nature of greetings between the two groups. The French salutation "Bonjour / Bonsoir" significantly diverges from the Russian counterpart "Good morning / Good afternoon / Good evening," accentuating the inherent formality prevalent in the Russian communication style. It is considered impolite for a French individual to omit the honorific terms "Monsieur, Madame, Mademoiselle" in conjunction with the greeting. Notably, French and Russian greetings vary in their customs. For instance, in France, handshakes are typically reserved for encounters involving unfamiliar or unfamiliarized individuals, while greeting acquaintances is accompanied by a kiss on the cheek. In contrast, Americans often pose the question "How are you?" expecting responses like "Fine / Great!" connoting a sense of optimism, a sentiment which is deemed exaggerated and uncharacteristic within French and Russian cultural contexts. In these cultures, an individual from France might instead respond with "Pas mal / ça va," while a Russian counterpart would likely affirm, "It's fine / Everything is fine / Fine." Although Russian and French communication cultures share similarities in their utilization of greeting formulas, the conspicuous distinction lies in the greater frequency of greetings observed among the French, often coupled with a smile.

The acquisition of cultural concepts during foreign language learning provides students with an opportunity to enhance their understanding of the lifestyles and perspectives of the individuals belonging to the target language's corresponding country. It is crucial to expose learners to diverse speech communication patterns and cultural norms in order to foster an

appreciation for the inherent variations in intercultural interactions. Acknowledging these cultural differences will assist students in navigating intercultural exchanges more effectively.

When engaging in intercultural communication, it is imperative for students to cultivate an acceptance of diverse cultures, including their values, merits, and advantages. This highlights the significance of mutual understanding in the realm of intercultural communication, which can be achieved through a deep comprehension of the interlocutor's culture, coupled with sincere recognition and respect for it.

Textbooks are an important source of cultural knowledge. For example, the "Across cultures" textbook published by Longman focuses on regional studies and the culture of the English-speaking world. It provides an opportunity for students to compare the life and culture of English-speaking countries with their own, along with tasks for speech development and vocabulary consolidation.

Another textbook, "Dictionary of Britain" published by Oxford, is a dictionary-reference textbook. Its primary goal is to help learners acquire a foreign language while exploring the culture of English-speaking countries.

Additionally, there's the "Fluent Forever" textbook by Gabriel Wyner. This textbook explains effective methodologies for learning a foreign language, including principles of intercultural communication.

These textbooks serve as a valuable resource for acquiring foreign language skills and gaining insight into diverse cultures and their particularities. Students are equipped with comprehensive information regarding customs, traditions, etiquette, behavioral norms, and communication subtleties prevalent in the country.

In addition to textbooks, various media are also sources of cultural knowledge, such as radio and television broadcasting, periodicals and foreign literature, multimedia and educational tools, and the Internet. It will also be useful to study the history and art of the country of the studied language in order to gain deeper cultural knowledge. The reflection of national culture can also be found in folklore and literature. It is possible to expand the intelligence and erudition of students through participation in various online conferences, various projects and meetings, courses, workshops,

as well as, of course, through the possibility of connecting to foreign libraries of different countries.

So, we understand that foreign language culture is a complex and multifaceted concept consisting of language and culture. At the moment, Russian education is faced with the task of functional learning of a foreign language, which contributes to its use for intercultural communication. After all, language is an element of culture in all its manifestations.

Comparative analysis of socio-cultural phenomena has become more accessible with the integration of role-playing games as a pedagogical tool. This pedagogical approach encourages students to express different cultural perspectives and views. During education they can deepen the understanding in different points of view and develop their critical thinking. Teaching culture in foreign language classes depends on its behavioral part, i.e., in which the rules of both linguistic and non-linguistic behavior are fixed (gestures, intonation, facial expressions, pantomime, the influence of interlocutors on each other through images).

For example, if we get acquainted with the forms of gratitude in the lesson, a teacher must explain to students that compliments are the national specifics of British politeness. The British make them much more often than the Russians. In England, a compliment is usually accepted with gratitude and reciprocity, and not, as is often done in Russia, with distrust and with the conviction of the interlocutor to the contrary.

According to O.P. Netroglova, the late 20th century witnessed a significant transformation in the understanding of culture due to the restructuring of society's spiritual life. This shift emphasized the crucial role of culture in societal existence, which consequently gave rise to the establishment of professional cultural education. Consequently, a new ideal for future specialists emerged, commonly referred to as a "man of culture." The continuous development of this concept occurs within the framework of ideological diversity, comprising various mediums for the innovative manifestation of individuality. Consequently, professional cultural education adopts a personalized approach that prioritizes the individual's unique qualities. Novel concepts in cultural education have arisen, exemplified by the notion of a specialist dedicated to uplifting the socio-cultural milieu.

O. P. Netrogolova notes that today the training of future specialists in the socio-cultural sphere is carried out in higher schools in such specialties as: "Cultural Studies", "Social Pedagogy", "Tourism", "Museum studies", "Linguistics". "The object of professional activity of specialists in the socio-cultural sphere is the socio-cultural environment, which is a spiritually saturated cultural space, the most important condition for the self-development of the cultural life of a person, a social group, and the territory as a whole" [2].

Therefore, we understand that future specialists will need to be able to translate societal values, needs, norms, preferences and behaviors. We should learn how to select inherited values, determine their place and role in solving problems of development of society and culture. It is important to pay attention to innovations aimed at updating, creating and enriching cultural values and norms. Innovations also influence the creation of a favorable cultural environment and stimulate innovative movements in the socio-cultural sphere. "The idea of developing cultural education was initially formed within the framework of professionally artistic, and then professionally cultural education by the ideals of a carrier and translator of a certain type of worldview" [2].

Conclusion

Cultured people are those who desire and appreciate mutual understanding and achievements with people from other cultures and are open to intercultural communication in foreign languages. The important task of forming a respectful attitude to a foreign culture actualizes the purpose of learning a foreign language – to give

students an idea of the universality of any language in order to form a person's communicative needs and respect for the languages and cultures of the peoples of the country of the studied language, which affects the formation of personality. Analyzing the work of scientists, we see that state documents have legislated the role of domestic education as the basis of socio-economic and spiritual development of Russia, showing its importance in preparing young people for successful entry into society, into the cultural world and educational space.

Understanding the ideas and concepts of Cultural Studies leads to the following conclusion. The scholars agree that foreign languages should be studied in the context of culture. Incorporating cultural information within each foreign language lesson is imperative as it serves to generate interest in acquiring a new language, instill a heightened motivation to delve deeper into linguistic knowledge, facilitate understanding of the daily lives of individuals from the country associated with the language, and foster appreciation for its culture. The inclusion of cultural studies within the realm of foreign language education holds promising prospects for both general education and the broader sphere of academia, as it aids in equipping students to engage effectively in cross-cultural exchanges.

The cultural idea in teaching foreign languages is still in the focus of attention of scientists and quite a large number of teachers, philologists and methodologists continue to agree that the cultural potential is a strategic task of the subject "Foreign language", which means that the study of foreign languages must necessarily take place in the context of culture.

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